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Collection number	Fieldwork bed number	Identification	Figured	3D model
IGM	LD1			
IGM 14091	LD1-01	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>		
IGM 14092	LD1-02	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>		
IGM 14093	LD1-03	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>	Figures 8.11-8.13	
IGM 14094	LD1-04	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>		
IGM 14095	LD1-05	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>		
IGM 14096	LD1-06	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	Figures 3.1-3.3	SA1-A
IGM 14097	LD1-07	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>	Figures 8.8, 10.1	
IGM 14098	LD1-08	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14099	LD1-09	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>		
IGM 14100	LD1-10	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>	Figures 8.9-8.10	
IGM 14101	LD1-11	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	Figures 6.11-6.13	SA3-B
IGM 14102	LD1-12	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14103	LD1-14	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>		
IGM 14104	LD1-15	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>	Figures 9.1-9.3, 10.2	SA3-B
IGM 14105	LD1-16	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14106	LD1-17	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>		
IGM 14107	LD1-18	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>		
IGM 14108	LD1-19	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>		
IGM 14109	LD1-20	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>		
IGM 14110	LD1-21	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14111	LD1-22	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	Figures 3.4-3.6	
IGM 14112	LD1-24	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14113	LD1-25	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14114	LD1-26	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14115	LD1-27	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figures 14.9-14.11	
IGM 14116	LD1-28	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14117	LD1-29	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14118	LD1-30	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>		
IGM 14119	LD1-31	<i>Roadoceras roadense</i>	Figure 6.4	
IGM 14120	LD1-33	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>		

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IGM 14121	LD1-34	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14122	LD1-35	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	
IGM 14123	LD1-36	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	
IGM 14124	LD1-38	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>	
IGM 14125	LD1-39	<i>Demarezites quirozii</i>	
IGM 14126	LD1-40	<i>Pseudagathiceras spinosum</i>	Figures 5.6, SA3-C 7.1-7.3
IGM 14127	LD1-41	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	
IGM 14128	LD1-42	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14129	LD1-43	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	Figures 5.5, 6.14-6.16
IGM 14130	LD1-44	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	
IGM 14131	LD1-45	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	
IGM 14132	LD1-46	Ammonoid	
IGM 14133	LD1-47	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14134	LD1-48	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14135	LD1-49	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14136	LD1-100	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>	Figures 4.2, SA1-C 5.2
	LD2		
IGM 14137	LD2-01	<i>Pseudagathiceras difuntense</i>	
IGM 14138	LD2-02	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14139	LD2-03	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14140	LD2-04	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14141	LD2-05	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14142	LD2-06	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14143	LD2-07	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	
IGM 14144	LD2-08	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14145	LD2-09	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14146	LD2-10	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14147	LD2-11	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14148	LD2-12	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14149	LD2-13	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14150	LD2-15	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14151	LD2-16	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14152	LD2-17	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
	LM1		
IGM 14153	LM1-01	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>	Figures 8.1- 8.3
IGM 14154	LM1-02	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>	
IGM 14155	LM1-03	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>	
IGM 14156	LM1-04	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>	

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IGM 14157	LM1-05	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>	Figures 8.4	
IGM 14158	LM1-06	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14159	LM1-07	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14160	LM1-08	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14161	LM1-09	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14162	LM1-10	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14163	LM1-11	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14164	LM1-12	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figure 9.8	
IGM 14165	LM1-13	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14166	LM1-14	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14167	LM1-15	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	Figures 16.3-16.4	
IGM 14168	LM1-16	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	Figure 16.6	
IGM 14169	LM1-18	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14170	LM1-19	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14171	LM1-20	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14172	LM1-21	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14173	LM1-23	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14174	LM1-24	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14175	LM1-25	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14176	LM1-26	Ammonoid		
IGM 14177	LM1-28	Ammonoid		
IGM 14178	LM1-29	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14179	LM1-30	Ammonoid		
IGM 14180	LM1-31	Ammonoid		
IGM 14181	LM1-32	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14182	LM1-33	Ammonoid		
IGM 14183	LM1-34	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14184	LM1-36	Ammonoid		
IGM 14185	LM1-37	Ammonoid		
IGM 14186	LM1-38	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14187	LM1-39	<i>Neocrimites plummeri</i>	Figures 6.8-6.10	SA3-A
IGM 14188	LM1-40	<i>Altudoceras</i> cf. <i>A. altudense</i>	Figure 4.5	
IGM 14189	LM1-101	<i>Altudoceras</i> cf. <i>A. altudense</i>	Figure 4.6	SA2-A
IGM 14190	LM1-103	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>		
IGM 14191	LM1-104	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>		
IGM 14192	LM1-106	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>		

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IGM 14193	LM1-107	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>	Figures 5.7, 8.5-8.7	SA4-A
IGM 14194	LM1-110	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>	Figures 4.3-4.4	SA1-D
IGM 14195	LM1-113	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14196	LM1-114	<i>Stacheoceras gemellaroi</i>		
IGM 14197	LM1-115	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	Figures 4.1, 5.1	SA1-B
IGM 14198	LM1-118	<i>Neocrimites plummeri</i>	Figures 5.4, 6.5-6.7	
IGM 14199	LM1-120	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14200	LM1-122	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14201	LM1-123	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14202	LM1-125	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14203	LM1-126	Ammonoid		
IGM 14204	LM1-128	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14205	LM1-129	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14206	LM1-130	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14207	LM1-131	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14208	LM1-132	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14209	LM1-133	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14210	LM1-134	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14211	LM1-135	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14212	LM1-137	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14213	LM1-138	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14214	LM1-139	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14215	LM1-140	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	Figure 16.5	
IGM 14216	LM1-142	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14217	LM1-146	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14218	LM1-147	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figure 13.3, 14.7-14.8	
IGM 14219	LM1-148	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14220	LM1-149	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14221	LM1-150	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figure 13.2, 14.5	
IGM 14222	LM1-151	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14223	LM1-152	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14224	LM1-153	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	Figures 9.7, 13.1	
IGM 14225	LM1-154	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	Figures 9.4-9.5	SA4-C

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IGM 14226	LM1-155	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figures 9.11-9.12	SA4-D
IGM 14227	LM1-156	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14228	LM1-158	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figures 14.1-14.2	SA4-E
IGM 14229	LM1-159	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14230	LM1-161	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14231	LM1-163	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14232	LM1-164	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14233	LM1-165	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14234	LM1-166	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14235	LM1-167	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	Figure 9.6	
IGM 14236	LM1-169	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14237	LM1-172	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14238	LM1-173	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14239	LM1-174	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14240	LM1-175	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14241	LM1-176	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14242	LM1-178	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14243	LM1-179	<i>Stacheoceras gemmellaroi</i>		
IGM 14244	LM1-180	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14245	LM1-182	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14246	LM1-183	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14247	LM1-184	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14248	LM1-185	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14249	LM1-186	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14250	LM1-188	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14251	LM1-189	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	Figures 13.5, 18.4	SA4-I
IGM 14252	LM1-190	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14253	LM1-191	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14254	LM1-192	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14255	LM1-193	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14256	LM1-194	<i>Roadoceras roadense</i>	Figures 5.3, 6.1-6.3	SA2-C
IGM 14257	LM1-195	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14258	LM1-196	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figures 14.3-14.4	SA4-F
IGM 14259	LM1-197	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figure 14.6	SA4-G
IGM 14260	LM1-198	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14261	LM1-199	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14262	LM1-200	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		

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IGM 14263	LM1-201	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	
IGM 14264	LM1-202	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	
IGM 14265	LM1-203	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14266	LM1-204	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	
IGM 14267	LM1-205	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14268	LM1-206	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14269	LM1-207	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14270	LM1-208	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14271	LM1-209	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14272	LM1-210	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14273	LM1-211	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14274	LM1-212	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14275	LM1-213	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14276	LM1-214	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	
IGM 14277	LM1-215	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	Figures 16.1-16.2
IGM 14278	LM1-216	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	
IGM 14279	LM1-217	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14280	LM1-218	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14281	LM1-219	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14282	LM1-220	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14283	LM1-221	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	
IGM 14284	LM1-222	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	Figures 9.9- 9.10
IGM 14285	LM1-223	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14286	LM1-224	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14287	LM1-225	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14288	LM1-226	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14289	LM1-227	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>	
IGM 14290	LM1-229	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14291	LM1-232	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14292	LM1-233	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>	
IGM 14293	LM1-234	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14294	LM1-235	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14295	LM1-236	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	
IGM 14296	LM1-237	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14297	LM1-244	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14298	LM1-245	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	Figures 18.1-18.3
IGM 14299	LM1-247	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>	
IGM 14300	LM1-248	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	
IGM 14301	LM1-249	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>	

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IGM 14302	LM1-250	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14303	LM1-251	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>	Figures 13.4, 16.7-16.8	SA4-H
IGM 14304	LM1-253	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		
IGM 14305	LM1-254	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14306	LM1-256	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14307	LM1-258	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14308	LM1-259	<i>Mexioceras guadalupense</i>		
IGM 14309	LM1-260	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
	LM2			
IGM 14310	LM2-03	Ammonoid		
IGM 14311	LM2-04	Ammonoid		
IGM 14312	LM2-05	Ammonoid		
IGM 14313	LM2-06	Ammonoid		
IGM 14314	LM2-07	Ammonoid		
IGM 14315	LM2-08	Ammonoid		
IGM 14316	LM2-09	<i>Strigogoniatites cf. S. kingi</i>	Figure 4.7	SA2-B
IGM 14317	LM2-11	<i>Waagenoceras dieneri</i>		
IGM 14318	LM2-12	Ammonoid		
IGM 14319	LM2-17	<i>Waagenoceras karpinskyi</i>	Figures 18.6-18.8	SA4-J
IGM 14320	LM2-18	<i>Waagenoceras karpinskyi</i>	Figures 13.6, 18.5	SA4-K
IGM 14321	LM2-20	<i>Waagenoceras karpinskyi</i>		SA4-L
IGM 14322	LM2-21	<i>Waagenoceras karpinskyi</i>		
IGM 14323	LM2-22	Ammonoid		
IGM 14324	LM2-103	<i>Paraceltites elegans</i>	Figures 5.8, 19.4-19.6	SA5-A
IGM 14325	LM2-109	<i>Paraceltites elegans</i>		
IGM 14326	LM2-112	<i>Cibolites cf. C. uddeni</i>	Figures 5.9, 19.7-19.9	SA5-B
IGM 14327	LM2-127	<i>Timorites schucherti</i>	Figures 19.2-19.3	
IGM 14328	LM2-177	<i>Timorites schucherti</i>	Figure 19.1	SA4-M
IGM 14329	LM2-187	<i>Waagenoceras karpinskyi</i>		
IGM 14330	LM2-255	<i>Waagenoceras karpinskyi</i>		
	LM3			
IGM 14331	LM3-01	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>		
IGM 14332	LM3-02	<i>Mexioceras smithi</i>		

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IGM 14333	LM3-08	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>
IGM 14334	LM3-09	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>
IGM 14335	LM3-10	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>
IGM 14336	LM3-12	<i>Neogeoceras girtyi</i>
IGM 14337	LM3-13	<i>Eumedlicottia burckhardti</i>
IGM 14338	LM1-145	<i>Waagenoceras girtyi</i>
